

Prototype of an Interactive Toy from Lego Robotics Kits for Children with Autism

Authors : Ricardo A. Martins, Matheus S. da Silva, Gabriel H. F. Iarossi, Helen C. M. Senefonte, Cinthyan R. S. C. de Barbosa
Abstract : This paper is the development of a concept of the man/robot interaction. More accurately in developing of an autistic child that have more troubles with interaction, here offers an efficient solution, even though simple; however, less studied for this public. This concept is based on code applied thought out the Lego NXT kit, built for the interpretation of the robot, thereby can create this interaction in a constructive way for children suffering with Autism.

Keywords : lego NXT, interaction, BricX, autismo, ANN (Artificial Neural Network), MLP back propagation, hidden layers

Conference Title : ICIRA 2014 : International Conference on Intelligent Robotics and Applications

Conference Location : Amsterdam, The Netherlands

Conference Dates : May 15-16, 2014